

EFFECT OF EARTHQUAKE ON DOMESTIC WATER SUPPLY IN KUTCH REGION (GUJARAT)

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SYNOPSIS

A severe earthquake occurred on the 26th January, 2001 in the Kutch region of Gujarat (India). Along with the other civil engineering structures, dams were also damaged. Most of these dams are earthen dams. Drinking water storage will be severely affected in the summer due to this.

The paper attempts to discuss the effect of earthquake on few such dams and its subsequent effect on the drinking water supply. Amongst the most affected dams are Rudramata, Tappar, Shivilakha, Suvi, Fatehgadh, Chang and Kaswati, which are domestic water storage as well as irrigation schemes. Rudramata and Tappar have been repaired while others had to be cut due to inability to repair due to short time period.

The top soil layer around the reservoirs of these dams contain fine sand. Due to the high permeability of these soils, substantial ground water recharge takes place resulting into the rise of ground water table in the surrounding areas. Many of the villages depend upon ground water for their domestic demands. So, the villages around the dams which have been cut will be seriously affected for their domestic water requirement, in the coming summer while the areas around Rudramata and Tappar will have sufficient recharge for ground water as well as storage for surface supply.

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*** ABOUT THE BHUJ EARTHQUAKE**

A disastrous earthquake of a magnitude (ML) 6.9 struck Bhuj and adjoining areas of Kutch district of Gujarat in the wee hours on 26th January, 2001. It's severity was so high that thousands of people were killed and several thousand injured. It also caused extensive damage to civil engineering structures. The highly damaged areas covered various talukas of Kutch district like Bhuj, Bhachau, Anjar, Rapar, Gandhidham etc as while there was lesser damage in parts of Saurashtra, parts of north Gujarat and in far away cities like Ahmedabad, Surat, Jamnagar and Bharuch. Amongst the areas outside Gujarat, the earthquake was felt in other parts of India like Bombay, Jodhpur, Lucknow and Peshwar etc. This earthquake attains significance because it was located very near to an urban conglomeration, the historical city of Bhuj, situated in the heart of the largest district of the state.

*** DAMAGES TO DAMS IN KUTCH DISTRICT**

The shallow focus seismic activity of the recent earthquake has also caused considerable damages to the existing medium and minor irrigation cum water supply schemes in Kutch district.

Kutch district is a drought prone area having low average annual rainfall. The number of rainy days are also less compared to the other parts of Gujarat. In the last 10 years, the average annual rainfall is still less. Looking to the drinking water demand, irrigation schemes are also being used for water supply to the surrounding areas. In the year 2000-2001, the Government of Gujarat has ordered reservation of sufficient quota of water in all irrigation schemes to meet the summer demand. In the Kutch region, water is not available in large quantities and looking to the topography and the scattered population, it is also not possible to provide water with tankers in all the areas. So, it is highly necessary to have a sufficient storage in the reservoirs of all dams.

Due to the earthquake on 26th January, 2001, the following irrigation cum water supply schemes are severely damaged.

1. Rudramata
2. Fatehgadh
3. Suvi
4. Tappar
5. Shivilakha
6. Chang
7. Kaswati

The details of the damages of each of the above mentioned dams is as follows. Plate 1 shows the photographs some of the damages to these dams

*** Rudramata Dam**

The Rudramata Dam is situated across the river Khari near village Nokhani in Bhuj taluka of Kutch district. The earthen dam has a height of 37m and a length of 875m. The gross storage capacity of the reservoir is 64.74 Mm³. There are two non-gated spillways, one 137.16m long and the other 290.7m long ogee shaped spillway with a stilling basin type energy dissipator. The dam was completed in 1960 and the height was raised again in 1992 to make up for the settled portion of the dam top.

Damages Observed

Longitudinal cracks were observed through out the length of the dam on the u/s slope at various chainages.

Ch 100 m	1.2 m deep, 20 cm wide
Ch. 180 m	2.5 m deep, 25 cm wide
Ch. 200 m	1.4 m deep, 20 cm wide
Ch 250 m	1.6 m deep, 10 m wide
Ch 280 m	9 m deep, 15 cm wide and d/s slope
Ch 330 m – 390 m	U/s slope failure in a length of 50 m approx. and displaced pitching.

Ch 410 m	1.2 m deep cut, initially this part had settled in past which was reexecuted before 15 years.
Ch 480 m – 520 m	Along the crest of dam.

Many transverse cracks over the top of the dam and some settlement along the slopes were observed. Seepage was observed at the downstream toe of the earthen dam near ch 330 m. Water pool was observed between ch 300 to 400 m beyond the d/s toe.

Cracks were also observed in the earthwork behind the abutment. The wing walls were damaged and the masonry joints in the abutment walls were opened. The foot bridge and the HR cabin were also severely damaged.

*** FATEHGADH DAM**

The Fatehgadh Dam is situated across the river Malan near the village Fatehgadh of Rapar taluka of Kutch District. The maximum height of the earthen dam is 11.28m and has a total length of 4130m. The gross storage capacity of the reservoir is 7.45 Mm³. The dam was completed in the year 1982.

Damages Observed

- * The earthen dam had longitudinal cracks along the top of the dam. Moving animals further aggravated very deep rain cuts on the slopes of the dams.
- * Transverse cracks of about 2cm width were seen at certain locations. At locations between ch 2100m to 3300m, multiple cracks having width 30 cm and depth of about 50 cm were observed on top of the dam.
- * Settlements in the u/s slope pitching as well as multiple cracks along the first berm were observed. At the u/s edge of the dam, 1.5m deep crack was observed.
- * A prominent crack of width 40 cm and depth 1.4m was seen in the centre of the dam extending upto 10m in one stretch.

- * At ch 3750m, earth work on u/s has slid due to slope failure close top of the dam by about 3m.
- * The d/s most end of the left side of training wall is completely damaged.
- * Construction joints of wing walls and training walls have widened at the top.
- * Parapet wall over both the wing walls of the spillway is damaged.
- * The HR cabin is completely damaged.
- * The top circular slab of the HR cabin got separated from the support and parapet walls of the approach bridge have fallen.

* **SUVI DAM**

It is a composite dam on the river Suvi situated near the village Suvi in the Rapar taluka of the Kutch district. The earthen dam is 4.5 km long with ogee waste weir. The gross storage capacity of the reservoir is 10.46Mm³. The dam was completed initially in the year 1969. The original section of the dam was raised by about 1m recently.

Damages Observed

- Transverse cracks were seen on the top of the dam.
- The parapet wall is crushed and crumbled in most of the length.
- Pitching is seen bulged due to slope failure on u/s of dam.
- The top width of earth dam at ch 500m is reduced apparently.
- There is subsidence of earthwork on the reservoir side and the top width has been reduced to 2.3m.
- There are deep cuts measuring about 2m depth from ch 5300ft to 5400ft.
- Between ch 5500ft and 5600ft, top of earth work has settled by 1m and a central crack is seen on the top of the dam.
- Between ch 5600 ft and 5700ft, the u/s slope has totally settled. A portion of earthwork of about 40m in width and 25m height on the u/s has totally failed and water has entered in such damaged area.

- Training walls both on u/s and d/s on both flanks have been raised by about 1m or so. The said raised portion is cracked and separated. At some locations the raised wall has fallen.
- Glacis is ogee shaped with chute having two slopes. At the junction of the ogee and chute, crack is formed.
- On u/s apron two to three distinct cracks are formed along the length of spillway. Certain stones have also broken into two pieces.

* TAPPAR DAM

Tappar Dam is constructed across Sakora river near village Tappar in Anjar taluka of Kutch District. It is a composite dam with maximum height of 31.70m. The length of the earth dam is 4053.65m with a gross storage capacity of 48.81Mm³

. The dam was completed in 1975 and provides water to Anjar, Kandla and Gandhidham.

Damages Observed

- * Surface drainage arrangement and kerb stones are damaged and broken at many places on d/s top edge of earth of dam in the entire length. At several places the masonry blocks of 35cm X 35cm got separated from earthwork. Top longitudinal drain has also toppled towards d/s.
- Longitudinal/parallel cracks in a length of 400m on top of dam are observed on the pumping station.
- A longitudinal crack is noticed from ch 1740m upto spillway along the u/s slope of earth dam close to the top.
- Transverse cracks on u/s slope between the first berm and top of the dam are seen near the jack well.
- A 1.5m deep longitudinal crack on the first u/s berm beyond ch 920m onwards is noticed.
- The u/s berm at R.L. 33.53m shows the signs of liquefaction of sand layer below in the reach from the jack well and spillway.
- At ch 600m a water pool on first u/s berm in a length of 30m is seen. Several wide longitudinal cracks are also developed. Fountains are reported to have occurred at many locations in the u/s portion of the bund.

- At both the junctions, the earth dam has settled by 15cm and longitudinal cracks on top of the dam are seen.
- The u/s riprap between berm at R.L. 35.36m and R.L. 43.28m has settled by about 1.0m.
- Minor settlement is seen and connection between d/s wall and glacis slab is loosened.
- Both side junctions with earth dam appear to have been disturbed.
- At the interface of the spillway and earthen dam, cracks in masonry have been noticed.
- HR cabin has totally crumbled.
- Piers caps have been detached and piers have settled. The distance between the pier caps and the failed pier face is about 1.0m.
- Parapet is badly damaged.

* SHIVLAKHA DAM

It is a water supply scheme. The earthen dam is constructed across river Kochri near Badalghar village in Bhachau taluka of Kutch district. The maximum height of the earth dam is 20m. The dam was completed in the year 1958 for supplying water to 33 villages.

Damages Observed

- Longitudinal cracks are observed all along the earthen dam and the dam is found to be seriously damaged.
- Dam is completely damaged in the river gorge portion where water spread in the reservoir is very close to the u/s toe of the earth dam.
- The u/s slope has slid and the failure plane lies d/s of the centre line of the earth dam. Pitching is disturbed at many places in gorge portion.
- Heaving is observed in the d/s slope of the earthen dam at many places in the gorge portion.

* CHANG DAM

It is a dam built across the river Chang near village Nilpur in Bhachau taluka of Kutch district. The maximum height and length of earthen dam is 17m and 1440 m resp. The gross storage capacity of the reservoir is 6950m³. The project was completed in the year 1959.

Damages Observed

- Complete failure of the earth dam in the river gorge portion for a length of more than 150m is seen.
- Settlement of top of the dam (15m) and settlement as well as sliding of u/s slope of earth dam is observed.
- The u/s slope has developed wide vertical cracks in 100m length at various levels.
- Sloughing of earthen dam towards the reservoir in about 200m length is observed.
- Wide cracks in the right hilly abutment are observed.

*** KASWATI DAM**

The Kaswati dam is situated across rier Kaswati near village Lodai in Bhuj taluka of Kutch district. The earthen dam has a maximum height of 8.81m and a length of 1454.5m. The construction of the dam was completed in 1976.

Damages Observed

- Transverse cracks are observed form ch 300m onwards at the top of the dam.
- Longitudinal cracks observed at ch 625m to 1280m are 5cm wide and 50 cm deep at the top of the dam.
- Heavy pitching settlement and disturbance is observed at Ch 625m, 720m, and 890m at both u/s and d/s slopes.
- From ch 800m to 1200m the cracks at the top of the dm separates earth slope in vertical fashion in 1 to 1.5m depth.
- HR cabin well has crumbled.
- Masonry between staunching rings is cracked.
- Approach bridge is settled. Concrete bearing at top of pier is cracked.
- Approach bridge girder is sagged and reinforcement is exposed.

* CONCLUSIONS

Of the above mentioned dams, Kaswati, Chang, Shivilakha, and Fatehgadh have been cut due to lack of time for repair before the monsoon. Suvi dam had been repaired and was kept at about half the storage capacity but it failed due to the after shocks.

As major portion of the Kutch district has porous sandy geological strata, the areas around the reservoirs of these dams are recharged for ground water which is generally used during the summer. But as many dams have been cut, there will be no storage of water this year and thus no ground water recharge either. As a result there will be a dual effect on the drinking water supply for the Kutch region. Looking to the topography, it is not possible to supply water in tankers to the scattered population. Also the downstream portions of these dams will suffer water shortage due to lack of recharge.

Looking to the above scenario, a serious problem regarding the water supply will be experienced in the coming summer season. The district is already suffering drought condition since past few years. All this only aggravates the drinking water supply problem.